

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Radio-chemo-immunotherapy in locally advanced NSCLC is ready for “prime time”!

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The integration of immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) has revolutionized lung cancer treatment, particularly for stage III unresectable non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Chemoradiotherapy (CRT) has been the standard to manage local recurrences for a long time and to prevent metastasis in these patients. The pivotal PACIFIC trial in 2017 demonstrated the efficacy of durvalumab, a PD-L1 inhibitor, as maintenance therapy post-CRT. Durvalumab significantly improved both overall survival (OS) and progression-free survival (PFS), with 5-year OS rates of 42.9% compared to 33.4% with placebo. Patients treated with durvalumab also exhibited a reduced risk of brain metastases and extended time to distant metastasis.

Sequential versus concurrent immunotherapy remains a subject of ongoing investigation. While concurrent CRT with durvalumab is now the standard of care, studies suggest that earlier initiation of immunotherapy may lead to improved outcomes, as seen in the PACIFIC subgroup analysis. Trials like DETERRERD and KEYNOTE 799 explore alternative ICIs, such as atezolizumab and pembrolizumab, alongside CRT, showing similar efficacy. Additionally, the GEMSTONE 301 trial in China highlighted sugemalimab's role in extending PFS, though OS differences were inconclusive.

Real-world evidence, including the PACIFIC-R study, continues to validate durvalumab's efficacy, especially in PD-L1 positive patients. Overall, ongoing research aims to refine the sequencing and combination of CRT and immunotherapy to optimize survival and quality of life in patients with stage III unresectable NSCLC.

Keywords: Lung cancer, Radiotherapy, Chemotherapy, Immunotherapy, NSCLC

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